

COMPARATIVE-CONTRASTIVE STUDY OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17275471>

Abstract. The present article elucidates the issues of studying phraseological units in the world linguistics. Different approaches to the study of phraseologisms were worked out by the world linguists. The study of phraseologisms in different fields of linguistics have been shown.

Key words: phraseology, phraseological unit, field, stable combination.

Phraseological units play an important role in enriching the vocabulary of any language. Despite the fact that phraseological units have been actively used in the vernacular language since ancient times, they have not yet been studied thoroughly as an object of linguistics research. Currently, there is an increasing number of studies devoted to the issue of phraseological units in the field of phraseology. The reason for this is the development of various new areas of linguistics. As the fields of linguistics develop, the study of language issues through new areas is also relevant and of particular importance. The reason for this is the establishment of new areas such as linguocultural studies, cognitive linguistics, pragmatics, discourse analysis and communicative linguistics. Therefore there is a need to study phraseological units according to the requirements of these areas. In this, the previously undiscovered aspects of phraseological units are highlighted. For example, the study of phraseological units through the field of linguistics and cultural studies reveals not only the aspects of language in the interrelation of language and culture, but also the characteristics of the people speaking this language. The comparative study of interlingual phraseological units allows observing the emergence of language units according to the traditional customs and habits of the nations speaking these languages. The study of phraseological units from the perspective of cognitive linguistics shows that the concepts formed by phraseological units are reflected in the minds of a particular language speaker through such concepts as national worldview and linguistic worldview, while the concepts associated with each phraseological unit are embodied in the minds of the people and the national worldview is differentiated, determining the thinking of representatives of this nation. Therefore, the phraseological units of each language demonstrate the characteristics inherent in the nation speaking this language.

According to the French scientist S.Mekri [15], the study of phraseological units in modern linguistics occupies a key place in the image of language. We can

agree with this scientist and admit that in new areas of linguistics, great attention is paid to the image of language. In terms of linguocultural studies, the relationship between the image of language directly and the culture of the nation, in cognitive linguistics, the image of language through the consciousness of the speaker of the language, and in communicative linguistics, the image of language with speech has become the object of research of most scientific works.

Since the field of phraseology is recognized as a developing field, attention began to be paid to the problems of this field in the 50-60s of the last century. Of course, even before these years, the nature of phraseological units was studied in one way or another. But it was not recognized as an independent direction. Since many scientists and researchers consider the field of phraseology to be independent, we think that we should pay attention to the discussion of this issue. Because phraseology is not an independent direction of linguistics, but is studied as a separate section within the discipline of lexicology. Although phraseology is studied as a section of lexicology, it makes possible to shed light on all the laws of the language. Therefore, we emphasize that phraseology can be recognized as an independent section of the field, not as an independent field, because it did not emerge from the discipline of lexicology as an independent field. Phraseology is a discussion, and when linguists put the object of research of phraseology in the center, there were two opinions. That is, it was recognized that the study of phraseology issues is divided into two areas:

1. Phraseology in a broad sense is associated with the study of stable compounds, various structures of word combinations, and sentence structure. Researchers such as L.A.Bulakhovsky[3], N.M. Shansky[13], S.G.Gavrin[5] conducted their research in this area.

2. Phraseology in a narrow sense covers only works devoted to the study of stable compounds, phraseological units, and V.V.Vinogradov[4], Sh.Balli[14], F. de Saussure, O.S.Akhmanova[2] were famous for their research and studies in this area.

It should be said that we have already mentioned the founders of these areas, but at present the number of works carried out in these two areas is increasing and makes a huge contribution to the development of linguistics.

Phraseological units, by their nature, are used figuratively, so their study is carried out using various methods and techniques. Sh. Balli was the first to study phraseological units stylistically. B.A.Larin[7] recommended various methods for the study of phraseology. V.M.Mokienko[8], having studied phraseology historically, approached the study of phraseological units in Slavic languages from

a diachronic aspect. M.Gross [16] and representatives of his school dealt with the syntactic issues of phraseology in developed. M.T.Tagiev[11] paid attention to the grammatical and lexical properties of phraseological units. While Russian linguists comprehensively studied the issue of classifying phraseological units and their lexical and semantic properties, these issues of phraseology were not given much attention by linguists from Great Britain and the USA. In English linguistics, the linguist L.P.Smith, who focused on the study of stable combinations and phraseological units, described them as “idioms”. In Russian linguistics, N.N.Amosova[1] was the first to pay attention to the issue of classifying phraseological units in English. Then A.V.Kunin, having comprehensively interpreted the issues of English phraseology, created Russian and English phraseological dictionaries. A.V.Kunin described the aspects of occasional and permanent use of phraseological units, and on the basis of the English language, he covered the lexical and speech aspects of phraseological units.

Also, the issues of phraseology are widely studied in the comparative aspect. In particular, T.F.Fedulenkova[12] conducted a comparative-typological study of phraseological languages in a comparative manner.

In the field of linguistics and cultural studies, phraseology was first studied by M.L. Kovshova[6] and V.N. Teliya[10], who made a great contribution to the field of linguistics. The units within the framework of German languages, identifying allomorphic and isomorphic features of phraseologisms. A.I.Smirnitsky[9] also contributed to the study of phraseology in the comparative-contrastive aspect. In particular, this scientist studied the phraseology of the English and Russian field of gender studies has developed, and currently phraseological units with gender signs are also being distinguished. This shows how widely the field of phraseology is developing.

To sum up, it should be said that the study of phraseological units during two centuries has touched upon different aspect of it.

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